

multiplied by a factor of 5.95 to get protein content. Protein fractions were estimated on the basis of solubility in water (albumin), sodium chloride (globulin), ethyl alcohol (prolamin), and sodium hydroxide (glutelin). Lysine content was measured using trinitrobenzene sulfonic acid reagent. Protein fractions and lysine content were calculated as percent of grain.

Protein content increased in all treatments. The highest protein content was obtained with 600 kg pyrite/ha and 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha.

Fractionation revealed that the major

Effect of pyrite and fertilizers on brown rice protein quality. Faizabad, India, 1985–86 kharif.

Character (%)	Range	Mean	CD at 5%	Character	Coefficient of correlation ^a
Protein	8.00–9.00	8.58	0.40	Protein vs albumin	-0.46
Albumin	0.53–0.74	0.62	0.07	Protein vs globulin	-0.32
Globulin	0.55–0.77	0.69	0.09	Protein vs prolamin	0.55*
Prolamin	0.32–0.65	0.51	0.14	Protein vs glutelin	0.76**
Glutelin	6.09–7.13	6.65	0.50	Prolamin vs glutelin	0.65**
Lysine	0.22–0.30	0.26	0.04	Protein vs lysine	-0.81**

^a * = significant at 5%, ** = significant at 1%.

amount of protein was in the form of glutelin (6.65%) (see table). Higher fertility slightly increased the prolamin and glutelin fractions. Lysine content

decreased with increased pyrite and NPK. Protein content was positively correlated with prolamin and glutelin and negatively correlated with lysine. □

Response to nitrogen of rice in sodic soil

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We studied the influence of N level (0, 60, 120, and 180 kg/ha) on yield in highly barren sodic soil without amendment. Soil was sandy loam with pH 10.3, 90% exchangeable sodium, 0.35 meq exchangeable Ca + Mg/100 g, 30 kg available N/ha, 21 ppm Olsen's

extractable P, and adequate available K in the 0–15 cm layer.

Damoder (CSR-1) variety was transplanted 16 Jul 1981 and 1982. Zinc sulfate at 5.5 kg/ha with one-third N as urea was applied at transplanting, with 1/3 N at 25 and 1/3 N at 50 d after transplanting. The crop was harvested 17 Nov 1981 and 16 Nov 1982.

Grain and straw yields increased significantly with N level (Table 1). The N content of grain and straw also increased (Table 2). □

Table 2. N content in grain and straw by N level. Karnal, India, 1981–82.

N level (kg/ha)	N content (%)			
	1981		1982	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
0	1.08	0.28	1.00	0.33
60	1.22	0.30	1.04	0.44
120	1.33	0.33	1.13	0.47
180	1.44	0.35	1.30	0.53
CD (0.05)	0.10	0.04	0.08	0.05

Table 1. Effect of N level on yield and yield attributes. Karnal, India, 1981–82.

N level (kg/ha)	1981				1982				pH at 0–15 cm after harvest in 1982		
	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers/hill	Panicle length (cm)	Yield (t/ha)		Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers/hill	Panicle length (cm)		Yield (t/ha)	
				Grain	Straw					Grain	Straw
0	83.4	7.8	14.4	1.3	2.4	98.7	6.1	14.9	1.4	2.3	9.8
60	95.1	11.5	15.6	2.2	3.7	113.0	10.9	17.3	2.5	4.2	9.8
120	105.5	13.1	16.4	2.9	4.9	117.9	12.5	17.7	3.0	5.3	9.7
180	111.0	14.5	17.0	3.6	5.9	124.8	13.8	18.5	3.4	5.9	9.7
CD (0.05)	6.5	0.9	0.8	0.4	0.6	7.2	1.1	0.7	0.4	0.6	–

Comparative efficiency of puddling implements

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We evaluated the performance of different puddling implements — rotary power tiller, iron puddler, iron plow,

country wooden plow, and wooden puddler — during the 1982–84 monsoon seasons and their effect on yield in newly terraced land.

The experiment was in a randomized block design with five replications. All implements except the rotary power tiller were bullock drawn. The plots were puddled with two criss-cross passes except with the country wooden plow, which had the farmer practice of four

passes. Plot size was 9.6 × 4.2 m. Soil was clay loam, lateritic with pH 5.6 and 1.19% organic C.

After puddling, Jaya was transplanted in early Jul at 20 × 15-cm spacing. The crop was fertilized with 100–22–41 kg NPK/ha. All the P and K and 40% N were applied at transplanting. The remaining N was applied in two equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation.

In 1983, yield was significantly